

presence of intramolecular H-bond in the ligands¹. The absence of this ν_{O-H} ligand band in ir spectra of the Pd^{II} complexes gave an indication of the

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL DATA OF Pd^{II} COMPLEXES OF α -OXIMINO BENZOYLACETARYLAMIDE SEMICARBAZONES AND THIOSEMICARBAZONES

R	Compd.	Analysis % :	
		Found	(Calcd.)
H	Pd(C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₅ O ₃) ₂	14.28	18.72
		(14.30)	(18.55)
o-CH ₃	Pd(C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₅ O ₃) ₂	13.68	18.08
		(13.63)	(17.88)
o-Cl	Pd(C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₃ Cl) ₂	13.25	17.16
		(12.95)	(16.99)
o-OCH ₃	Pd(C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₅ O ₃) ₂	13.39	17.26
		(13.09)	(17.18)
2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	Pd(C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₅ O ₃) ₂	13.58	17.45
		(13.16)	(17.27)
H	Pd(C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₅ O ₃ S) ₂	13.88	18.12
		(13.56)	(17.79)
p-CH ₃	Pd(C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₅ O ₃ S) ₂	13.61	17.36
		(13.33)	(17.18)
p-Cl	Pd(C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₃ S) ₂	12.70	16.58
		(12.46)	(16.36)
o-OCH ₃	Pd(C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₅ O ₃ S) ₂	12.48	16.55
		(12.60)	(16.53)
2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	Pd(C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₅ O ₃ S) ₂	12.71	16.76
		(12.66)	(16.61)

replacement of hydrogen of the oximino group by the metal. The shift of ν_{NO} ligand band from 940–970 to 1 150–1 180 cm⁻¹ in the complexes indicated the coordination through N and not through O of oximino group, and the complexes contained the nitron (N→O) linkage which is known to absorb at about 1 200 cm⁻¹ as a very strong band². Such shift of ν_{NO} ligand from about 1 000 to about 1 200 cm⁻¹ showed the nitronic type linkage in many oxime complexes³⁻⁵. The strong band around 1 595–1 640 cm⁻¹ in the ligands was assigned to $\nu_{C=N}$ ⁶; in the complexes, this band appeared around 1 560–1 590 cm⁻¹. The lowering of $\nu_{C=N}$ indicated coordination of 1-N of the semicarbazide/thiosemicarbazide moiety. The ν_{N-N} ligand band around 1 010–1 040 cm⁻¹ shifted to higher frequency in the chelates by 25–40 cm⁻¹ indicating the monodentate linkage of N–N residue⁷. The presence of C=S bands at 800–860 and 1 040–1 090 cm⁻¹ in the free ligands as well as in chelates suggested non-involvement of this group in coordination of the metal⁸. The ligands therefore acted in a bidentate manners and not as a tridentate one. The infrared spectra of the ligands and complexes revealed bands around 3 300, 3 100 and 3 400 cm⁻¹, indicating secondary association, primary association and free N–H vibrations of amides, respectively⁹. The strong bands in the ligands and complexes around 1 650, 1 540 and 1 300 cm⁻¹ are attributed to amide I, II and III, respectively⁹.

The electronic (reflectance) spectra of these complexes exhibit two bands. One broad band (in some cases a shoulder) was observed in the range

520–585 nm (19 231–17 094 cm⁻¹) and the second and more intense band was observed in the range 375–410 nm (26 667–24 390 cm⁻¹), which may be assigned to $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1A_{2g}$ and $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1B_{1g}$ transitions, respectively. The band positions are in agreement with those generally observed for square-planar Pd^{II} complexes^{10,11}. All the Pd^{II} complexes were found to be diamagnetic.

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Complexes of Dioxouranium(II) and Thorium(IV) with Potentially Tetradentate Schiff Bases

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IN the present communication, we report the synthesis and spectral properties of a few uranium(VI) and thorium(IV) complexes with Schiff bases,

R = H, OCH₃

derived from 2,6-diaminopyridine and salicylaldehyde or vanillin.

Experimental

Uranyl nitrate hexahydrate and thorium nitrate hexahydrate were of A.R. grade. Salicylaldehyde, *o*-vanillin and 2,6-diaminopyridine were purified by conventional methods.

Preparation of Schiff base ligands: Salicylaldehyde (or *o*-vanillin) and the diamine were mixed in 2:1 molar ratio in ethanol and refluxed for 1–2 h. After the reaction, solidification occurred rapidly on cooling. The solid was separated and crystallised from methanol.

Preparation of complexes: A warm ethanolic solution of uranyl nitrate (or thorium nitrate) hexahydrate (0.001 mol in 25 ml) was added with stirring to a warm ethanolic solution of the Schiff base (0.002 mol in 25 ml). The resulting solution was refluxed for about 1–2 h. The complex separated on cooling was filtered washed with ethanol and dried in vacuum over fused calcium chloride. Uranium and thorium contents in the complexes were determined gravimetrically¹. Nitrogen was estimated microanalytically by Dumas method.

Conductance measurements were done with a Elico CM-82 conductivity bridge using DMF as solvent. Infrared spectra (KBr) of the complexes and ligands were recorded with a Perkin-Elmer 81 spectrometer in the region 4000–180 cm⁻¹. The results are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND CONDUCTIVITY DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd *	Analysis % :		Molar conductivity Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹
	Found/(Calcd.) M	N	
[UO ₂ (DAP-Sal)(NO ₃) ₂]	33.98 (34.29)	11.96 (12.10)	41.36
[UO ₂ (DAP-Van)(NO ₃) ₂]	31.01 (31.56)	10.89 (11.14)	43.14
[Th(DAP-Sal)(NO ₃) ₄]	29.27 (29.74)	14.17 (14.35)	38.41
[Th(DAP-Van)(NO ₃) ₄]	27.58 (27.61)	13.14 (13.33)	41.81

*DAP-Sal: C₁₂H₁₁N₃O ; DAP-Van: C₁₂H₁₃N₃O₂

Results and Discussion

All the complexes were intense by coloured substances, insoluble in most of the organic solvents, but soluble in DMF. The molar conductance values determined in DMF at the concentration 10⁻³M indicated their non-electrolytic nature². The ir spectra of Schiff bases have shown³ a fairly intense band around 1610 cm⁻¹ (C=N) which shifted in the complexes to the region 1630–1650 cm⁻¹ indicating coordination of the azome-

thine group⁴. The band in the region of 3500–3000 cm⁻¹ in the Schiff bases is assigned to the NH₂ stretching frequency. The splitting of the NH₂ stretch in the complexes makes it imperative that NH₂ has taken part in the coordinate bond formation. A strong and sharp band for Th^{IV} complexes appeared in the region 1260–1240 cm⁻¹ assigned to the covalent NO₃ group⁵. This is however not observed in case of UO₂^{IV} complexes. Two characteristic frequencies, 950–890 and 830–820 cm⁻¹ can be predicted⁶ for UO₂^{IV} ion in the uranium complexes. The intense broad band found in the region of 510–530 cm⁻¹ in UO₂^{IV} complexes is ascribed to the ν_{U-N}, and the band at 560–580 cm⁻¹ is assigned to ν_{Th-N} vibration in Th^{IV} complexes⁷. The data available on the pure ν_{M-O} prescribe the region between 500 and 400 cm⁻¹ for M—O stretching⁸. The band at 440–460 cm⁻¹ in the complexes was assigned to the M—O stretching mode⁹. This is the indicative of metal-oxygen band formation with the oxygen of the *o*-OH group of the ligands.

The electronic spectra of all the complexes in solution indicated no distinct bands in the 330–750 nm and the typical band expected due to the UO₂^{IV} group at 390–450 nm seems to be masked by the fairly strong metal ligand charge transfer bands¹⁰ and ligand π-π* absorption bands appearing at 520 and 340 nm, respectively. These bands are of little help in elucidating the structure.

Thermogravimetric measurements showed the absence of water in these complexes. The complexes were very stable at room temperature, the initial decomposition temperature being in the range 200–230°. At higher temperature (above 800°), the complexes lose ligands and anions in definite stages and finally forming U₃O₈ or ThO₂.

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